

SEIZURES AMONG PATIENTS WITH NEUROMYELITIS OPTICA SPECTRUM DISORDER (NMOSD)

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Abstract

Seizures in cases of neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorder (NMOSD) are relatively rare syndrome. That's why they are poorly studied and understood. The aim of this article was to describe the prevalence, possible pathogenesis, clinical significance and outcome of epileptic seizures, associated with NMOSD.

Results: The prevalence of epileptic seizures in cases with aquaporin 4 antibodies positive (AQP4+) NMOSD varies between 0 to 6.25% and among Myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein antibody-associated disease (MOGAD) is estimated between 5.6 and 24%. They are more frequent in pediatric population. Seizures can develop as initial sign of the disease, can be the co-existing syndrome with other cortical or spinal signs at onset or can develop during the course of the disease, in most of the cases during attacks/relapses. The type of seizures varies, but the most frequent are focal motor seizures, followed by generalized clonic-tonic ones, although convulsive and nonconvulsive epileptic status, epilepsy partialis continua, painful tonic spasms and nonconvulsive focal seizures are also described. The pathogenesis of seizures in NMOSD is poor understood, although autoimmunity might play important role. The prognosis of seizures is relatively good in most of the cases on immunotherapy, although symptomatic epilepsy and even refractive epileptic status and epilepsy are also described. It is better in AQP+ NMOSD and double seronegative NMOSD than in MOGAD.

Conclusions: Epileptic seizures, even rare and in most of the cases with good prognosis, are one of the important manifestations of NMOSD. Seizure pathogenesis in such cases is unclear, although autoimmunity might play important role.

Keywords: seizures, neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorder (NMOSD), Myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein antibody-associated disease (MOGAD), autoimmunity.

Neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorder (NMOSD) is uncommon autoimmune demyelinating disease of the central nervous system (Hor, 2020, Aljarallah, 2025). The prevalence of the disease is 0.5-4/100 000, although it might be up to 10/100 000 in certain racial groups (Hor, 2020)

About 70% of patients have anti-aquaporin4 IgG antibodies, known as aquaporin 4 positive NMOSD (AQP4+). The detection of these antibodies is highly specific serum marker for the disease (Aljarallah, 2025). AQP4+ has high female to male ratio (9:1), mean age of onset about 40 years, the prevalence is higher in non-white racial groups and the course is relapsing (Hor, 2020).

About 15-50% of seronegative patients with NMOSD have antibodies to myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein (MOG) and they are recognized under the term of MOGAD (Aljarallah, 2025). MOGAD has sex ratio close to 1:1, it is most prevalent in children (adults 1,3/1 million; children 3.1/million) and the course of the disease could be monophasic or relapsing (Hor, 2020).

There is a certain group of patients with NMOSD negative for AQP4-IgG and MOG, which is called double seronegative NMOSD (dnNMOSD) (Wu, 2023; Aljarallah, 2025). The median age of onset of dnNMOSD ranged from 32 to 43 years, sex ratio is close to 1:1 or there is a slight female predominance (Wu, 2023). The disease could be monophasic or chronic (Wu, 2023).

Although very rare, there is a very small proportion of patients positive to AQP4-IgG and MOG,

known as dual positive NMOSD (Spiezia, 2022; Lalwani, 2025). Most of the double positive patients are females, with high grade disability, poor prognosis, they develop extensive involvement of spinal cord and most of them have brain lesions, some of them show additional peripheral nerve involvement (Spiezia, 2022; Lalwani, 2025).

Seizures in cases of NMOSD are relatively rare syndrome of the disease. That's why they are poorly studied and understood. The aim of this article was to describe the prevalence, possible pathogenesis, clinical significance and outcome of epileptic seizures, associated with NMOSD.

Prevalence of epileptic seizures.

The prevalence of epileptic seizures in cases with AQP4+ NMOSD varies between 0 to 6.25% (Hamid, 2018; Yao, 2019; Etemadifar, 2021; Ertürk Çetin, 2024; Li, 2025). They are more frequent in children (6.25%), than in adults (0%-0.72%), see table 1 (Etemadifar, 2021; Ertürk Çetin, 2024; Li, 2025).

The prevalence of seizures among MOGAD patients is higher than AQP4+ NMOSD and is estimated between 5.6 and 24% of all patients, they are more prevalent in pediatric population (Hamid, 2018; Yao, 2019; Zhong, 2019; Cross, 2021; Li, 2022; Ertürk Çetin, 2024; Wang, 2024; Li, 2025).

The prevalence of seizures among dnNMOSD patients is unknown.

Lalwani et al. (2023) described 3 double positive NMOSD cases among 1935 patients with NMOSD, one of which (33%) with recurrent seizures.

The time of seizure onset.

Seizures in cases with AQP4+ can be the initial symptom of the disease (Perez Giraldo, 2023; Romozzi, 2024), they can develop at the onset with other cerebral, optic or spinal cord symptoms (Hamid, 2018; Bu, 2022; Li, 2025), but in most of the cases, they occur during the follow up or during acute attacks/relapses (Yao, 2019; Etemadifar, 2021; Aryal, 2023; Li, 2022; Li, 2025). In most of the cases, seizures are acute and patients rarely develop symptomatic epilepsy (Etemadifar, 2021; Bu, 2022; Aryal, 2023; Li, 2025).

The onset of seizures in MOGAD depend on the MOGAD phenotype. They can develop as a symptom of cortical encephalitis, along with headache, fever, changes in awareness (Hamid, 2018; Zhong, 2019; Cross, 2021; Valencia-Sanchez, 2023; Ertürk Çetin, 2024; Wang, 2024). Rarely, mostly among pediatric MOGAD, seizures may develop as initial separate symptom of the disease (Yao, 2019; Yılmaz, 2019; Zhong, 2019; Yang, 2024; Wang, 2024; Jączak-Goździak, 2025). Cases (most of them pediatric) with MOGAD and anti - N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor encephalitis (NMDAR) are also described (Cross, 2021; Guzmán, 2023; Wang, 2024, Du, 2019). 16-100% of them are presented with epileptic seizures and even epileptic status at onset and many of them developed symptomatic epilepsy.

The majority of MOGAD patients develop seizures firstly during the relapses or even between them, months or even years after the initial diagnosis (Hamid, 2018; Haddad, 2019; Yao, 2019, Cross, 2021; Liu, 2021; Li, 2022; Ertürk Çetin, 2024; Wang, 2024). The other rare presentation of MOGAD, associated with seizures is leukodystrophy-like presentation (Wang, 2024; Biswas, 2026). It is more often seen in children than adults and is characterized by severe neuroinflammation and demyelination. In most of the cases, such phenotype represents acute demyelinating encephalomyelitis, but some cases don't meet the criteria and now they are considered as severe form of MOGAD.

About ¼ to 1/3 of all cases with MOGAD and seizures develop symptomatic epilepsy and need concomitant antiepileptic treatment (Valencia-Sanchez, 2023; Wang, 2024). The onset of seizures among dnNMOSD is poorly understood although patients might develop their seizures during the course of the disease, but not as initial syndrome (Cross, 2021; Sachde, 2024). Lalwani et al. (2023) describe a case with double positive NMOSD with seizure onset initially after the first severe symptoms.

Types of epileptic seizures in NMOSD.

Patients with AQP4+ NMOSD develop mostly focal convulsive seizures (Hamid, 2018; Yao, 2019; Romozzi, 2024; Li, 2022; Li, 2025). They are rarely presented with painful paroxysmal tonic spasms (Aryal, 2023), epilepsia partialis continua (Romozzi, 2024), generalized tonic-clonic seizures (Etemadifar, 2021; Bu, 2022), multifocal seizures or nonconvulsive status epilepticus (Perez Giraldo, 2023). Electroencephalography (EEG) might be normal (Aryal, 2023) or it can show generalized discharges (Etemadifar, 2021), continuous high-amplitude theta/delta waves (in epilepsia partialis continua, Romozzi, 2024), slow waves (mostly in cases with seizures with focal origin; Yao, 2019). In most of the cases they are acute and patients don't need

concomitant antiepileptic treatment, although acute immunomodulatory treatment with corticosteroids, plasma exchange and intravenous immunoglobulins and disease modifying drugs are recommended (Hamid, 2018; Yao, 2019; Romozzi, 2024; Li, 2025).

Patients with MOGAD might present with status epilepticus, generalized seizures or seizures with focal origin (Hamid, 2018; Haddad, 2019; Yao, 2019, Zhao, 2020; Cross, 2021; Liu, 2021; Li, 2022; Valencia-Sanchez, 2023; Ertürk Çetin, 2024; Yang, 2024; Wang, 2024; Rubin, 2025). Pediatric patients are more likely to experience status epilepticus (Rubin, 2025). MOGAD patients may also develop refractory status epilepticus (Vaingankar, 2025). Severe cases might develop Rasmussen-like clinical picture with refractory epilepsy and brain atrophy (Misu, 2025). They had worse prognosis in regard of seizure recurrence than those with AQP4+ NMOSD and some of them need concomitant antiepileptic treatment (Haddad, 2019; Zhao, 2020; Liu, 2021; Wang, 2024; Misu, 2025), although according to Yao et al. (2019) antiepileptic drugs do not significantly reduce the occurrence of acute epileptic seizures. EEG might show diffuse slow waves, slowed background, intermittent low amplitude fast waves, interictal focal spikes, focal sharp-wave complex and asymmetry focal slow waves, although it could be normal, depending on the exact seizure type and the time of the examination (Yao, 2019; Zhong, 2019; Liu, 2021; Yang, 2024; Jączak-Goździak, 2025). Focal onset seizures and generalized seizures are described in cases with dnNMOSD (Cross, 2021; Sachde, 2024), however they can be the only symptom of relapse (Sachde, 2024).

Seizure pathogenesis among patients with AQP4 NMOSD is poor understood. Although, the relatively rare seizure development in cases with AQP4 NMOSD, the frequency of seizures is above this, reported in normal population. Moreover, most of the seizures are developed during relapses and are focal in origin, which suggest some specific links between the disease and epileptogenesis. In some cases, the development of seizures can be explained by the existence of massive demyelinating cortical/subcortical plaques (Yao, 2019; Perez Giraldo, 2023; Romozzi, 2024). However, in some cases, seizures are not associated with massive cerebral lesions and the link between AQP4+NMOSD and seizures can be more complex. AQP4 is widely expressed on the plasma membrane of astrocytes, surrounding brain capillaries and play important role in regulation of ion homeostasis (K⁺) and glutamate release (Bonosi, 2023). AQP4 might also operate as a metabotropic receptor, interacting with glutamate receptors and modulating their activity and might regulate the function of NMDAR (Bonosi, 2023). So antibodies against AQP4 receptors might dysregulate the function of AQP4, leading to neuron excitation and lowering the seizure threshold or even developing the epileptic focus. This might explain why patients with AQP4 + NMOSD show relatively good prognosis in relation to their epileptic seizures with starting of anti-inflammatory medications, even in cases without concomitant antiepileptic drug treatment.

MOGAD can be presented as monophasic or multiphasic cortical encephalitis with extensive cortical involvement and frequently with focal, multifocal and generalized clonic-tonic seizures (Valencia-Sanchez, 2023; Wang, 2024; Misu, 2025; Trewin, 2025). The frequency of MOGAD cortical encephalitis is about 1% in adult cases and 4% in pediatric population (Trewin, 2025). In some cases, it can lead to catastrophic epilepsy, non-responsive to classical antiepileptic treatment (Vaingankar, 2025; Trewin, 2025). The pathophysiology of cortical encephalitis in MOGAD is poorly understood. The extensive leptomeningeal inflammation and intracortical demyelination, along with activated microglia and macrophages play important role for the development of encephalitis and epileptogenesis in such cases (Valencia-Sanchez, 2023; Wang, 2024; Rubin, 2025).

The seizure pathogenesis in cases with MOGAD leukodystrophy-like presentation is unclear (Wang, 2024; Biswas, 2026), although severe neuroinflammation and demyelination might play the most important role.

The epileptic pathogenesis in MOGAD +NMDAR cases is complex and unclear. Patients with such phenotype are divided into two categories – patients that develop anti MOG and anti NMDAR simultaneously at a certain stage of the disease and those in which these antibodies are successively detected during the course of the disease but not simultaneously (Du, 2024). The clinical picture in second category doesn't differ from that of mono antibody-positive patients (Du, 2024). Du et al. (2024) proposed the mechanism of MOG and NMDAR encephalitis. According to them (Du, 2024) some triggers can cause oligodendrocyte damage (through immune mimicry) so “MOG and NMDAR can leak through blood-brain barrier to the peripheral

immune system, which can start to produce MOG and NMDAR antibodies simultaneously; NMDAR antibodies presumably bind to NMDAR expressed on the neurons and induce internalization and dysfunction of NMDAR and MOG antibodies presumably bind MOG expressed on the myelin, leading to myelin injury and subsequent demyelination”. The simultaneous co-occurrence of both antibodies somehow changes the pathogenesis and subsequent clinical picture of the isolated autoimmunity. Patients with MOG + NMDAR show better prognosis than those with NMDAR only (Du, 2024; Wang, 2024).

Some patients with MOGAD might show epileptic seizures without brain substrate, so called isolated seizures (Zhong, 2019; Du, 2024; Yang, 2024, Wang, 2024). Although unknown, some authors suggested that such seizures are due to autoimmune related lowering the seizure threshold in MOGAD brain, associated with neuroinflammation, oligodendrocyte damage and possible neurotransmitter imbalance (Zhong, 2019; Liu, 2021; Wang, 2024). This hypothesis is supported by relatively good prognosis in regard to epilepsy among cases on immunotherapy, even without antiepileptic treatment.

Conclusions: Epileptic seizures, even rare, are one of the important manifestations of NMOSD. They are more frequent in pediatric population and in cases with MOGAD and can be presented at onset or can develop during the course of the disease. Focal onset seizures are the most frequent type, followed by generalized tonic-clonic seizures. In most of the cases the prognosis in regard to seizure occurrence is good, although refractory epilepsy is also described. Epileptic pathogenesis in cases with NMOSD is poor understood, although the autoimmunity is suggested to play important role. Patients with seizures respond well to immunotherapy.

Table 1.

Literature review - cases with NMOSD and seizures.

Study	Study population/ Case report	Seizure incidence	Description
Etemadifar, 2021	137 AQP4+	0.72%	Generalized tonic-clonic during follow up, EEG – generalized discharges
Romozzi, 2024	Case report 52 years old man with AQP4+	NA	Focal seizures (initial sign), treated with LEV, 5 months after the first seizure Epilepsia partialis continua, treated with Diazepam, VAL, Phenytoin, Rituximab EEG - right parietal continuous high-amplitude theta/delta waves
Li, 2025 (pediatric)	94 MOGAD 16 AQP4+	9.3% 6.25%	Seizures of focal origin, rare Epileptic status, most of them during relapses
Jączak-Goździak, 2025 (pediatric)	Case report 17 years old MOGAD	NA	Partial seizures (onset), treated with VAL and Topiramate; EEG - slow theta, several sharp and slow wave complexes; good recovery and discontinuation of AED Acute treatment with CS and IVIG, followed by low doses of CS and Azathioprine
Yao, 2019	61 MOGAD 565 AQP4+	21.3% 0.4%	>50% of seizures were single of focal onset; the most common abnormalities, associated with seizures were EEG – slow waves, cortical/subcortical lesions; long term AED did not significantly reduce the occurrence of acute epileptic seizures, which was 66.7% before and after treatment. Mycophenolate mofetil significantly reduced acute epileptic seizure occurrence

Bu, 2022	Case report of 54 years old female AQP4+	NA	Generalised tonic-clonic seizures and seizures with focal onset, encephalopathy and fever at onset; EEG – NA; acute treatment with pulse CS, followed by CS and mycophenolate mofetile, no AED used
Wang, 2024 (pediatric)	236 MOGAD	6.8% cortical encephalitis 5.5% overlap MOGAD+NMDAR 1.3 % Isolated seizures	Phenotype of cortical encephalitis at onset (16 patients, of them 15 with seizures) – convulsive seizures (14 patients), 1 patient with nonconvulsive seizures; 75% of seizures were bilateral clonic – tonic of focal origin; 52.3% status epilepticus; 68.8% had relapses during the first year; 5/16 patients were treated with AED; 9/16 patients were treated with IVIG, 6 patients were treated with pulse CS; MOGAD-NMDAR (13 patients) – 92.3% of them had seizures as initial syndrome; 11/13 (84.9%) had relapses during the follow up of 4 years. 7/13 received first-line immunotherapy (CS or IVIG). After the first relapse 10/11 patients were treated with specific immunotherapy (5/10 mycophenolate mofetil; 5/10 rituximab). 1 patient received regular IVIG and 1 azathioprine. Isolated seizures without any abnormalities on head imaging (3/236) 2 patients (66.6%) with focal motor seizures and 1 patient (33.3%) with focal motor seizures and focal secondary bilateral tonic-clonic seizures. 2 cases were with normal EEG, 1 case had focal spike-like slow waves in the sleep phase. 2/3 cases had relapses within the first 2 months and they were treated with immunotherapy.
Cross, 2021	21MOGAD and 20dnNMOSD	4.87%	Convulsions, headache, fever – cortical encephalitis, 1 of them had focal seizures at onset, 2 others – at follow up; 1 patient had MOG+NMDAR. EEG and AED treatment – NA
Lalwani, 2023 (study conducted among 1935 patients with NMOsD)	3 dual positive patients (AQP4+,MOG+) (case report)	33% (n=1)	27 years old female patient presented with bilateral optic neuritis (left>right) initially and subsequently relapsed following an episode of a seizure with left-sided hemiplegia
Perez Giraldo, 2023	Case report of 23 years old man, with disease onset at 12 AQP4+	NA	The initial syndrome - focal onset seizure with impaired awareness. During the follow up - recurrent multifocal seizures, focal seizures, nonconvulsive status epilepticus. The patient was treated with CS, plasmapheresis, rituximab. Because of immunodeficiency, treatment with granulocyte-colony stimulating factor was used. EEG – NA. AED treatment – NA.
Haddad, 2019	MOGAD Case report	NA	Initially the patient had of right-sided retro-orbital headache worse with lateral gaze, photophobia, and subjective decreased visual acuity, treated with pulse CS. 2 weeks after the treatment, the patient presented with focal seizures.
Yilmaz, 2019	Case report of 10 year-old girl MOGAD	NA	Onset with focal seizures, normal neurological status, EEG and head MRI, followed by gradually development of behavioral and personal changes within 2.5 months. The neurological status showed mild ataxia and drowsiness. On MRI - hazy and poorly demarcated lesions with gadolinium enhancement in the basal ganglia, supratentorial white matter, cerebral peduncles, cerebellum, and servical spinal cord. The patient was treated with IVIG and recovered completely with no relapses during the 6 month follow up.
Roszak, 2026	Case report of 19 years old female with MOGAD	NA	The initial symptoms were rapidly progressing memory and speech disorders. MRI - acute nodular demyelination in the left hemisphere. The patient was treated with pulse CS. 2 months later she was presented with several generalized epileptic seizures. The patient was discharged on oral CS and AED.

Ertürk Çetin, 2024	21 AQP4+ 56 MOGAD	0% 5.6%	No patient with AQP4+ had seizures. 5.6% of all patients with MOGAD had status epilepticus, most of them had recurrent focal convulsive seizures. Status epilepticus was observed at the onset or during the course of the disease.
Aryal, 2023	Case report of 68 years old man with AQP4+	NA	The initial symptoms of the patient were bilateral optic neuritis, stiffening of bilateral lower limbs, and weakness of bilateral upper limbs and urinary retention. He was treated with pulse CS, followed by oral CS and Azathioprine. Two months after, he complains of rapid painful tonic spasms bilaterally at lower limbs. EEG was normal during and inter attacks. He showed no response on gabapentin (900mg/d), diazepam and tizanidine and baclofen. Eslicarbazepine 200 mg once a day was added at the 7 th day with significant reduction of amplitude and frequency of spasms.
Hamid, 2018	100 AQP4+ 34 MOGAD	0.1% 14.7%	1 patient with AQP4+ presented with Focal epilepsy as initial sign. 4/34 (11.8%) MOGAD patients had encephalopathy, 2/34 (5.9%) had recurrent seizures, of them 1 had status epilepticus. 3/34 patients had generalized tonic-clonic seizures, 1 had partial seizures and 1 complex partial seizures. Of them, 4 patients were treated with mycophenolate mofetil (2 of them with mycophenolate mofetil only, 1 patient with mycophenolate mofetil + Rituximab and 1 patient with mycophenolate mofetil + CS), 1 patient was treated with oral CS only. 2 patients received AED during the follow up (1 of them was on LEV and 1 on LEV+carbamazepine).
Zhao, 2020	Case report of 30years women with MOGAD (onset at the age of 13 years)	NA	Initial syndromes – paresthesia, weakness of lower extremities (myelitis), treated with pulse CS and oral CS; 5 months later – optic neuritis, followed by several relapses with optic neuritis, treated with CS and occasionally IVIG and interferon beta. 7 years after the onset, she developed generalized seizures, treated with VAL. Brain MRI – massive T2 hyper-intense white matter lesions.
Sachde, 2024	28 years old women with dnNMOSSD	NA	Initial symptom – optic neuritis; Generalized tonic-clonic seizures 1 month after the onset; head and cervical MRI Multiple cortical subcortical hyperintensities involving bilateral frontal parietal and bilateral basal ganglia region without any post contrast enhancement; few multifocal long segment, intramedullary hyperintense lesions involving upper cervical cord at C2, C3 and C4 level with hyperintense signal in anterior aspect of medulla, no oligoclonal bands detected; pulse CS; LEV
Rubin, 2025	140 adult onset MOGAD 197 pediatric MOGAD	30.6% (pediatric) 7% (adult onset)	Pediatric patients are more likely to develop status epilepticus and encephalopathy, adults are more likely to have pleocytosis. 37.3% of patients had co-positivity with other antibodies (88.3% NMDAR). Adult-onset patients more frequently showed parietal lobe involvement and fewer temporal lobe lesions
Yang, 2024	6 cases with isolated seizures among MOGAD, 29-40 years old	NA	5/6 patients had simple motor seizures, 1 – complex motor seizure; 5/6 had single or multiple subcortical demyelinating lesions; 1 at basal ganglia. All were treated with pulse CS, followed by oral CS. All patients had concomitant AED treatment, most of them LEV. EEG at the time of admission showed symmetric diffuse slowing waves in 5/6
Valencia-Sanchez, 2023	19 cases with MOGAD cortical encephalitis	13.68% had seizures	2/19 had simple motor seizures of focal origin, 5/19 had complex motor seizures; 4 had simple nonmotor seizures; 2 generalised clonic-tonic seizures; 4/19 had secondary generalized seizures, 1 – epileptic status. The patients were treated with pulse CS 17/19; 1 with IVIG, 1 with plasma

	(6.7% of all MOGAD cohort)		exchange. 8/19 continued on AED, and 1 had drug-resistant epilepsy
Du, 2024	49 patients with NMDAR + MOGAD	51% had seizures	The most frequent syndromes were seizures and psychiatric syndrome. The symptoms were milder and less likely to progress to severe symptoms vs NMDAR encephalitis. visual impairment and limb weakness were less frequent in patients with MOG+NMDAR+ than in those with MOGAD, and MOG+NMDAR +often had manifestations such as psychiatric symptoms and seizures, which were atypical for MOGAD. 48/49 patients were treated with first line immunotherapy (pulse CS or IVIG or plasma exchange), 27/49 received combined immunotherapies. Rituximab and cyclophosphamide were used in 12/49. Sequential treatments were initiated in 24/49 patients, including rituximab (12/49), mycophenolate mofetil (10/49), and azathioprine (5/49) therapies. The recurrent rate of the disease was higher than NMDAR or MOGAD alone.
Zhong, 2019	58 patients with MOGAD	24%	11 (79%) subjects had seizure as the first symptom, and 3 (21%) developed seizure during the subsequent relapse. The types of seizure were generalized tonic-clonic seizure (n = 7, 50%), focal seizure with secondary generalization (n = 5, 36%), complex partial seizure with alternated conscious and facial twitching (n = 1, 7%), and simple partial seizure with focal left arm twitching (n = 1, 7%) Electroencephalogram (EEG) was abnormal among 15/58 (25.9%) subjects, including slowed background (theta to delta rhythm), intermittent low amplitude fast waves, focal sharp-wave complex and asymmetry focal slow waves.
Liu, 2021 (pediatric)	49 patients with MOGAD	24.5%	33.3% single seizures, 66.6% repetitive seizures, status epilepticus- 16.67%, focal onset 83.3%, generalized 16.67%; 66.67% abnormal EEG; 66.67 – slow waves, 62.5 – slow background, focal slow waves 37.5% and interictal spikes 25%
Legend: AQP4+ - aquaporin 4 positive neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorder, MOGAD – Myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein antibody-associated disease, dnNMO – double seronegative neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorder, NMDAR –anti N-methyl-D-aspartate receptors encephalitis, MRI – magnetic resonance imaging, EEG – electroencephalogram, AED – antiepileptic drug, VAL – valproic acid, LEV – levetiracetam, CS – corticosteroids, IVIG – intravenous immunoglobulins			

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